

Perception of Body Image on Self-Concept among Undergraduate Students in Nigeria: a Review

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Abstract

This is a conceptual paper that explores the complexities of body image, emphasizing the impact of digital media, mental health, and cultural standards on undergraduate students in Nigeria. It highlights how platforms like Instagram shape beauty standards, often leading to negative self-perceptions and mental health issues, particularly among young adults. The study examines shifting beauty ideals from thin-centric to slim-thick and the psychological effects of digital manipulation and unattainable beauty standards. It also considers the influence of Western beauty norms across different cultures, the role of social media in exacerbating mental health conditions like eating disorders and anxiety, and the emergence of body positivity and inclusivity movements as counter-narratives. The study advocates for a holistic approach involving media literacy, cultural sensitivity, and mental health support to address these concerns.

Keyword: Body Image, Self-concept, Undergraduate Students, Body Positivity

Introduction

Body image is a multidimensional construct encompassing how one thinks, feels, and acts toward one's body (Sarwer & Cash, 2008). It includes a person's perception of one's physical self and the thought and feelings, positive, negative or both, which result from that perception (Grogan, 2010). In the contemporary era, body image has become an increasingly complex and pervasive issue, with individuals grappling with the intersection of societal expectations, digital media influence, and mental well-being. Body image issues have impacted people of all ages, genders and cultures since the dawn of time (probably), Or at least since the dawn of the mirror. And especially since the advent of Instagram which has an endless supply of genetically blessed people or people flaunting their modified bodies (Youth Sense, 2023). The advent of social media has allowed the use of websites and applications to create and share content or to participate in social networking. Technological developments have given rise to various gadgets including smart-phones, tablets which have given to rise more exposure to all sorts of social media platforms. Living in a digitized era, communication has now become easier and faster with the emergence of various social applications available at the click of a button. While many may agree that social media has connected individuals globally, it has also been used to set standards of beauty for females, males as well as the other gender. This in turn has been known to affect the self-esteem of individuals with regards to body image, body modification and how they view themselves in society. In order to be accepted in society, females have to battle body image issues from a very young age, where thin is considered to be the ideal body type (Grabe et al., 2008). Although, Body image issues affect everyone including the old and the young but it is becoming increasingly more pronounced especially among the students as they are more conversant with the usage of social media and they are being constantly judged by social media audience and imaginary audience. Ghaznavi and Taylor (2015) described a new trend on social media which is called thinspiration; a slim body which is being portrayed as the ideal body type and which is also being enforced; most pictures of females within this trend are muscular and toned. Fitspiration content places a greater emphasis on muscular physique than thinspiration or bonespiration, which places more emphasis on the thin ideal.

The curvaceous form has been increasingly popular in recent times due to a variety of trends. The hashtags #thick, #thicc, and #slimthick are becoming more and more common on social media sites like Instagram, Twitter, and so on, which indicates this tendency (McComb & Mills, 2022). The term "curvy" lacks a precise definition; it is commonly used to describe plus-sized and overweight bodies, but it is also recognized in the media to mean having a thin waist and wider hips. Another way to conceptualize it would be as an oversized hourglass shape with a huge bust, a wide pelvis, and a narrow waist (Ahern et al, 2011). Research by Hunter et al. (2021) provided a quantitative assessment of this hourglass figure in terms of a waist-to-hip ratio (WHR) of less than 0.7. Slim-thick or hourglass bodies may be just as unrealistic and detrimental to women's body image as thin-ideal bodies, despite the fact that research on women's body image has not been done on this type of body. McComb (2022) proposed labeling this type of body type "slim-thick-ideal," combining an unrealistic exaggerated image of a flat and narrow waist with a big circumference around the hips and breasts, as an alternative to calling it plus-sized, average,

or curvy-slim, all of which have different meanings. This topic explores the intricate relationship between body image and various contemporary factors, shedding light on the challenges students face in cultivating a positive self-perception

Perception of Female undergraduate students' Body Image

Students these days feel at ease questioning conventional notions of beauty, viewing them as unattainable and unduly perfectionistic. They favour new trend of body modification and unnecessary standards set by celebrities and role models on social media. Beauty standards predated social media, but with the advent of filters and photo-editing applications, students now have the ability to curate an idealized self that conforms to unattainable beauty standards. This warps the truth about the human body and encourages viewers to strive for an unachievable ideal of beauty. Even in the media industry, images perpetuate the idea of "the perfect body." For example, Toke Makinwa's photos showed Brazilian Butt Lift, which was not indicative of the standard for Generation Z but rather of the idealized portrayal of the star. However, the opposite is true, as students use these stars' representations of themselves as a benchmark for beauty, thus, the difficulty. It is no secret that numerous celebrities and influencers have been exposed for altering their bodies on social media (Lauren, 2022).

Influence of Social Media on Perception of Students' Body Image

Social media especially social networking sites such as Facebook, Twitter, and Instagram have become a huge part of most student's lives. They easily yield and imbibe information found on these sites. A person's appearance is determined or influenced by many factors including genetics, biology, behaviour, character, beauty or ugliness and several other cultural standards. Due to these diverse and complex influences, the appearances of human beings often vary greatly but the standards set by social media has made a lot individuals including the students to question and doubt their self-image. Instagram for example is one of the social media platforms that is being used to distort reality; Instagram post is a photo or video that users share on the platform. Each post by a user appears on their followers' Instagram feeds and can also be viewed by the public when tagged using hashtags. Users can add a caption to each of their posts and use hashtags and location-based tags to index these posts and make them searchable by other users within the application. They can also like, comment on and bookmark others' posts, as well as send private messages to their friends via the Instagram direct feature (Babaleye et al., 2020).

In Nigerian society today, young females are especially pressured to conform to change their appearances or looks to conform to Instagram beauty standards and other social media networking sites. Consequently, young Nigerian females aim at adopting the body shape, size or complexion of some celebrities of their choice or their so-called role models and heroes and heroines on social media. The media has a way of prioritizing certain body image to look more attractive than some others such as extreme thinness, skinny, big breasts, buttocks and tiny waist for women and V-shaped muscled body for men. Hence, young females are on a daily basis confronted with the traditional and stereotypical ideals of social media beauty standards. For many of them who are just attaining the age of 18 it may be the first time they are allowed to make certain choices on their own. Such female youths are often faced with mixed messages regarding their value and the need to always look attractive. The pursuit to conform to distorted beauty ideals and body image is associated with different problems including lack of self-confidence and low self-esteem, among others. In the world of social media, users post content displaying their best selves. It is a digital escape for people to view each other's profiles and connect, but unfortunately, it can also lead to comparison. With celebrities and influencers editing their bodies and showing off their skin, body comparison and negative body image are inevitable. Negative body image includes disliking one's physical appearance, which can lead to low self-esteem and mental disorders like depression or anxiety. Beauty standards existed before social media, but the new establishment of filters and photo-editing apps allow teens and young adults to create an ideal version of themselves, aligning with unrealistic beauty expectations. These posts distort the reality of the human body and drive viewers to aspire to conform to an impossible beauty standard. Even in the professional world of media, images encourage the illusion of "the perfect body." Model Cameron Russell of Vogue told Verily Magazine that pictures of her in publications are not of the actual Cameron Russell, but rather an idealized representation of the model. It is no secret that a large number of influencers and celebrities have been found to have altered their physical appearance for social media. Adolescents and young adults are nonetheless, though, under constant pressure to live up to these expectations. According to BBC Future, women in particular frequently use social media to compare themselves to peers and celebrities. When attractive and well-known individuals despise their bodies, their admirers react by detesting their bodies even more (Lauren, 2022).

Social media personalities, actresses, musicians, models influencers, celebrities and even cross-dressers go through body modifications and it's becoming a pandemic rocking the entertainment industry. These body modifications range from Brazilian Butt Lift popularly known as BBL to liposuction, skin tightening, lips filling and so on. These body modifications have permeated and pervaded the social media and it is being consumed by the students who feel the standards set by these celebrities are the norm to follow; because these celebrities play the role of models to a lot of the students. With celebrities like Tonto Dikeh, Toke Makinwa, Mercy Eke, Iyabo Ojo becoming the torchbearers of the trend in the Nigerian entertainment

space and publicly flaunting their ‘new assets’, it was gathered that the wave is not confined to the glitz and glamour of celebrity life but steadily influencing young women, most especially the students across Nigeria to follow in their footsteps (Adebayo, 2023).

Digital Manipulation and the Illusion of Perfection

The pressure to be "perfect" is a reality that many students must deal with; whether it's from envying classmates who seem to breeze through schoolwork, wanting to fit in with the popular person, or wanting to be among the top athletes, nearly all students have felt the agony of feeling "less than" at some point. Although this is nothing new, since the start of the digital revolution, the pressure has increased exponentially. Students have virtually unrestricted access to a wide range of social media networks, all of which constantly update them on the lives of her peers, celebrities, influencers and actresses by showcasing what they want the people to see.

Social media like Facebook or Instagram allow individuals to follow each other and people who are well-known individuals with thousands of followers because of their attractiveness and sense of style—young people they have never met in "real life." These people pick their shots very carefully; they never share a horrible photo (and it's typically unclear if they alter them or not), they never dress inappropriately, they never seem to be having a "off" day, and they never seem normal in any manner. Essentially, these social media influencers introduce the unachievable standards that were formerly exclusive to high-end fashion models in glossy magazines into the everyday lives of individuals. As such, for many students, the pressure to emulate such impossible standards begins to feel very close to home and real in a way that prior generations never had to experience (Kaminsky, 2016).

Recent survey research from the Pew Research Centre indicates that most US teens (ages 13-17 years) have access to a smartphone (95%), and 45% report that they are online on a “near-constant” basis, commonly accessing sites such as YouTube (85%), Instagram (72%), Snapchat (69%), and Facebook (51%) (Anderson & Perin, 2018). Moreover, over half of US teens report efforts to scale back their use of social media (57%) or video games (58%), with girls specifically reporting that they spend excessive time on social media (47%) (Juang, 2018). A large, nationally representative survey of US youth (ages 8-18 years) similarly indicated high levels of media consumption, with respondents devoting on average of 10.75 hours daily (or over 7.5 hours daily after accounting for multitasking behavior) toward the use of entertainment media (Rideout et al., 2010). These high levels of media consumption are not limited to the US. Results from the World Health Organization's (2010) Health Behavior in School-aged Children Survey (across 30 countries) reported an average of 4.41 to 8.60 hours of screen time daily for boys and girls (Bucksch et al., 2016). These high rates of media consumption are concerning not only because of their associations with indicators of poorer health among youth, ranging from lowered self-esteem, well-being, and body image to symptoms of social anxiety and depression, but also because the widespread digital retouching of advertising imagery may exacerbate negative impacts of media by presenting unrealistic and unattainable standards for physical appearance and beauty (Richards et al., 2015). Indeed, digital photo retouching of advertising imagery is ubiquitous and often involves correcting perceived “flaws” in the appearance of featured models including modifying skin tone, minimizing signs of wrinkles or blemishes, or modifying their body size or shape. The impact of Photoshop is considerable. Photoshop has made a “once unattainable image of beauty and perfection much less a figment of the imagination and much more a tangible reality, leaving beauty in the hands of its digital creator (Brown, 2014). Although there are opportunities to intervene at the individual-level, such as by providing media literacy training to buffer the negative impacts of media exposure, a broader and likely more efficacious strategy requires intervention that targets the source-regulating digital retouching in consumer advertising to reduce the risk of harm to youth.

Cultural and Gender Perspectives on students’ Body Image

Sociocultural perspectives on body image assert that culture influences attitudes, behaviors and values regarding the body (Frederick et al., 2017). Western’s cultures are exerting much influence on how women perceive to be physically attractive and the attitude shown towards their body (Keery, 2004). Although body dissatisfaction and related consequences are thought to be a Western societal phenomenon; it has made its presence felt in developing countries (Goswami et al., 2012).

Body image perception also does not always correlate with actual nutritional status of individuals; which is a more objective assessment. Previous studies on body image satisfaction reported different prevalence rates of dissatisfaction with body image; 62% in Europe, 48.1% in Malaysia, 51% in Iran and 73.6% in Saudi Arabia (As-Sa’edi et al., 2016). In Nigeria, a survey reported a prevalence of 82.9% body image dissatisfaction among public and private school students in Benin, Edo State (Otakpor & Ehimigbai, 2016). In the past, thinness was associated with illness while being plump was associated with good health in some parts of Nigeria but in the twentieth century, thinness has become an indicator of good health, while, being overweight has been associated with diseases, unattractiveness and other characteristics (Grogan, 2021). Media can be a vehicle for the transportation of an idealized body. One way media exposure influences body image is through appearance-based

comparisons with popular media. This leads to body dissatisfaction because many women focus their attention on how their own appearances do not equate with idealized media (Tiggemann & Polivy, 2010).

In White-centred mainstream media, thin-ideal images of women's bodies are ubiquitous and widely advertised across various media channels, including magazines, social media and television (Gestos et al., 2018). Studies showed that beauty trends conveyed via social media have an enormous influence on a woman's self-image, not only in Western but also in Asian cultures (Jackson et al., 2016).

In particular, image-based social media channels, such as Instagram, present a monotonous body image that produces significant pressure on social media users. It was shown that exposure to attractive celebrities or peers increases body dissatisfaction and negative mood. This impact was interceded by a state appearance comparison (Brown & Tiggemann, 2016).

Studies have shown that body image is dependent on the internal projections of our body and body parts, and is seen as an important aspect of self-worth across the human life span. This is often evidence of an attempted conformity with parameters of beauty established in socio-cultural or non-personal contexts (Fitzsimmons-Craft and Bardone-Cone, 2012). In other words, what is believed to be the ideal body image in the mind of the individual will be projected out through the body image size he or portrays. Some years ago in Arabic culture, for example, an overweight body image was seen as desirable and a symbol of female fertility, whilst in many non-Western cultures being overweight and near clinical obesity may also be seen as a mark of beauty (Furnham and Alibhai, 1983). The same attitude was reported amongst Mauritanian women where obesity was culturally glorified, in Indian society where fatness had a positive effect on establishing alliances or finding a marriage partner, amongst Cameroonians who considered fatness prestigious, Moroccans who attributed fatness to good health, and in Fijian, Tahiti and Nauru Pacific cultures, where fatness is associated with beauty and fertility (Jumah and Dudah, 2007; Lau et al., 2006; Liimakka, 2014).

Mental Health Implications of students' Body Image

Today, social media is one of the most important factors contributing to the mental, emotional, physical and spiritual health of an individual. With the media constantly portraying ideal beauty and body image comparisons, the decisions of men and women's beauty choices are globally affected. Body image refers to a person's perception of their physical self and the thoughts and feelings, positive, negative or both, which result from that perception. Social media has had a major impact on the perceptual, affective, cognitive and behavioral aspects of body image by encouraging lean body patterns and delivering anti-obesity messages (Fardouly, 2020). Eating disorders determine a distorted relationship between the individual, their eating behavior and body shape (Cavalcanti et al., 2016).

Adolescence being a crucial age for positive and negative development of body image, the self-esteem and body dissatisfaction adolescents feel are known predictors of eating disorders (Voelker et al., 2015). Continuous pursuit for the perfect slender lean body may generate negative feelings which can result in a change in eating behavior, thereby increasing the chances of weight issues and eating disorders (Cecon et al., 2017). Social media portrays women who are slim as being more beautiful and successful compared to overweight women (Toriola et al., 1996). Body image misperception and dissatisfaction with body weight highlight an association between body dissatisfaction and psychological wellbeing (Moehlecke et al., 2020). Looking at images that correspond to the current ideal of beauty leads to negative effects on women's own body image (Frederick et al., 2017). There is a body of evidence showing that media consumption engenders a higher rate of body dissatisfaction and ultimately eating disorders in women. A range of negative psychological and physical health outcomes are associated with dissatisfaction, such as social anxiety, interest in aesthetic surgery and lower life satisfaction (Frederick et al., 2016).

In particular, image-based social media channels, such as Instagram, present a monotonous body image that produces significant pressure on social media users. It was shown that exposure to attractive celebrities or peers increases body dissatisfaction and negative mood. This impact was interceded by a state appearance comparison (Brown & Tiggemann, 2016). Social media comprises of social networking sites, image sharing sites, video hosting sites, community blogs, bookmarking sites and gaming sites. Fellow comparisons about self-image and appearances in teenagers have resulted due to social networking sites (SNSs) such as Instagram and Facebook (Mascheroni et al., 2015). Teenage girls engage in online self-presentation of posting selfies and sharing the outfit of the day pictures to differentiate themselves with their peers (Kaplan & Haenlein, 2010). Media images of ideal beauty standards influence the content and sharing of pictures teenage girls' post (Boyd, 2014). Individuals are constantly seeking feedback on SNSs through likes, followers and comments to uphold a perfect and stable image of themselves (Corcoran et al., 2011). Teenage girls are vulnerable to the upward comparison as it means that they need to improve their beauty standards, thereby leaving them dissatisfied with their physical bodies, having doubts about their self-worth and also driving them to self-harm behavior (Chua & Chang 2016).

Many experts in the field of childhood development believe that teenagers' vulnerability (resulting from the numerous changes they are going through), their need for peer approval, and the frequent comparisons they make between themselves and other people create the ideal environment for self-doubt. Many teenagers are particularly harmed by the false sense of perfection that social media presents. In addition, it often pushes them to pretend to be happy in order to "fit in" online rather than admitting their actual feelings of uneasiness and sadness. This phenomenon is so common that it was named "duck syndrome" by researchers at Stanford University in response to a spate of suicides among young adults in their college years who had previously given the impression of being model students. Duck syndrome is named after the way a duck looks to glide across the water with calm ease, but in actuality, its little legs are thrashing fiercely just below the surface. After more research, it was discovered that each of these children had created a properly thought-out social media post, complete with happy pictures and motivational sayings. Their Facebook and Twitter sites give the impression that they are carefree and that success comes naturally to them.

For many people, young or old, depression has long been an "invisible illness." However, the way social media pushes young people to communicate behind a mask of perfection produces a smokescreen that even the most understanding parents and friends frequently are unable to see through. Although the majority of specialists do not think that social media by itself may cause depression, it is increasingly clear that social media can help the condition, both by masking its symptoms and by making the depressed person feel worse about themselves. After all, a young person's social media feed serves as a continual reminder of who they believe they "should" be. Looking through their own carefully produced content can engender intense sentiments of living a lie and of never being able to live up to both their own public image and that of others. The cycle of despair and overachieving gets worse the more the young person looks at his or her "ideal self," the less palatable their imperfections appear in comparison (Kaminsky, 2016).

Balance in Body Positivity, self-concept and Inclusivity Movements among undergraduate students

In the attempt to cure negative body image, the body positivity movement actively pushes against unrealistic beauty standards. They aim to end the harmful consequences of negative body image by encouraging the portrayal of realistic beauty standards in the media (Lauren, 2022). The body positivity movement is the type of phenomenon that is intriguing to observe from a sociological perspective. Emile Durkheim (1903) theorized that society is kept together by something called collective consciousness, that is made up of beliefs and morals that are present to a group of people.

The body positivity movement is an example of the collective consciousness of our society shifting and evolving to account for new ideas developing in the social sphere. Many people have been hesitant to support the movement in the misconception that it intentionally contributes to physically unhealthy lifestyles. According to Forbes, the body positivity movement encourages inclusion, not obesity. "Personally, I think the movement is fascinating for the way that people have responded to it (Barrett, et al., 2007). Criticism of the movement is largely from people who are rooted in the collective consciousness surrounding body image and health. Everything that happens in society at a large scale has a systemic structure that needs much more work to change than the minds of individuals. That says something about how compelling the narrative put forward by the body positivity movement must be: it is affecting systemic change, and that is monumental. The inclusion of diverse bodies in media allows viewers to feel comfortable with their own bodies, especially when posting their own content. If people see bodies like theirs in campaigns, magazines, movies, and TV shows, they will accept their bodies to be a new standard of beauty. Therefore, breaking the unrealistic beauty standards of social media by popularizing different body types will produce more positive body image in teens and young adults (Lauren, 2022).

Conclusion

Self-concept and body image are complex, multidimensional problems that are influenced by a range of modern elements, such as social media, cultural norms, and society expectations. With the rise of social media, there is a greater emphasis on body image and a consequent rise in body dissatisfaction, particularly among younger generations such as undergraduate students in Nigeria. People's perceptions of themselves have been profoundly impacted by digital manipulation and the spread of unattainable beauty standards on these platforms, which frequently result in mental health issues.

Nonetheless, countering these harmful norms are movements like inclusion and body positivity, which support diversity, acceptance, and self-love. Maintaining surroundings that support a healthy perspective on body image, one that values mental health, celebrates diversity, and encourages healthy behaviors, both offline and online is critical.

However, the body positivity movement is not without its criticisms. Some argue that the movement can unintentionally promote unhealthy lifestyles by normalizing certain conditions, such as obesity, which may be associated with health risks. Despite this, the core intent of the movement remains focused on combating societal pressures that cause body dissatisfaction and promoting psychological well-being.

Recommendations

Some recommendations were made as regards the body image discussed above which are very paramount to mitigate and accentuate more on the scourge of influence of unfiltered social media, invasion of western culture and other factors. Below are some of the recommendations:

1. **Encourage the teaching of media literacy:** Media literacy initiatives should be incorporated into educational institutions to assist students in evaluating and comprehending the effects of digital content, filters, and photo-editing software. These courses ought to have a strong emphasis on identifying staged photos and unattainable beauty standards in order to promote a more grounded understanding of social media material.
2. **Encourage positive social media use:** Social media platforms should encourage positive body image content and create guidelines that promote authenticity over curated perfection. This can include policies to label digitally altered images, promote content diversity that showcases various body types, and highlight body-positive influencers.
3. **Regulate digital manipulation in media and advertising:** Governments and regulatory bodies should consider creating guidelines for digital manipulation in advertising and media, ensuring transparency when images are retouched or manipulated. Such regulations would help reduce unrealistic beauty standards and promote healthier body image perceptions among youth.

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